

What is User Experience to Science Gateways?

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Abstract—User experience (UX) has become a central concept in fields involving human-technology interactions. However, despite its widespread recognition in other domains, UX has not been widely adopted in the science gateway community, where the narrower concept of usability remains the dominant focus. This paper explores the potential value of integrating UX concepts and methods into the design and evaluation of science gateways, emphasizing the distinction between usability and UX. Through an interview study conducted with gateways personnel, we investigate their perceptions of UX and its relevance to their work. Our findings suggest that while usability is considered important, UX offers additional benefits by encompassing affective, contextual, and experiential factors that usability alone may overlook. By incorporating UX concepts and methods, science gateways could improve user satisfaction and engagement, and also enhance the design and maintenance of gateway projects. We argue that a broader adoption of UX can enhance the design process, aligning gateways more closely with the diverse needs and experiences of their users.

Index Terms—user experience, usability, science gateways, cyberinfrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

User experience (UX) is a core concept in fields that explore interactions between humans and technology, such as human-computer interaction (HCI), human factors engineering, and human-centered design. Despite decades of academic attention and its growing prominence in professional computing roles, UX has not seen widespread adoption within cyberinfrastructure research and science gateways. While the gateways community has increasingly focused on usability—a related but distinct concept—the broader UX perspective remains underexplored in this domain. Usability typically emphasizes performance metrics, such as how efficiently and effectively users can achieve specific goals within a system. UX, on the other hand, extends these concerns by incorporating affective, experiential, and contextual factors, offering new ways to think about user-system relationships.

User experience (UX) is a core concept in several fields dealing with interactions between humans and technology, including human-computer interaction, human factors engineering, and human-centered design. While the concept has been around for several decades in the academic literature [1], and has become increasingly popular as a professional role in computing fields [2], it has not seen the same prevalence in cyberinfrastructure and science gateways research and practice. The gateways community has seen increasing focus on usability [3], [4], which is a related but distinct

concept. Compared to the performance focus that usability has, the concept of UX includes an expansion on the concepts and methods of usability, offering new ways to think about relationships between users and computing systems. In this paper, we present some findings from an interview study with gateways personnel with the goal of understanding their perceptions of UX and its value for gateways. We provide a brief outline of the origins and development of UX, and also comment on potential value of incorporating more UX concepts and methods into the design and evaluation of science gateways.

II. BACKGROUND

The Human-Computer Interaction literature, where usability concepts and methods originated (e.g., [6]), has witnessed an expansion beyond simply the instrumental value of artifacts (i.e., their usability) to more focus on the *experience* of using them [5]. This expansion has encouraged thinking about topics like affect and meaning in addition to the traditional usability concerns of learnability, efficiency, and errors. In parallel to this expansion, there has also been an increasing emphasis on the *design* of artifacts rather than just their use. Traditional views of usability place little emphasis on the design process and methods that are employed to create software, instead focusing on the *evaluation* of software that is created [7].

Usability can be defined as “the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use” [9]. Usability testing essentially tells us how well users can perform tasks that are given to them, and how confused, frustrated, or efficient they are. Focusing on usability alone still leaves many critical details about a product out—e.g., whether users actually want to use it, who the target user group is, whether it fits an important need, and how it should be designed. Other science communities have taken notice of the value of adopting a UX lens—e.g., the Pistoia alliance, a life sciences research organization, creating a model of UX heuristics to be used by other life science groups [8]. As evidenced by MacDonald et al. [10], UX practices have brought significant value to the field of libraries by revolutionizing how library services and resources are designed, delivered, and experienced by users. While usability is still a critical concept for gateways, adopting a broader set of UX concepts, methods, and practices could provide significant value for science gateways.

III. METHOD

We performed semi-structured interviews with gateway teams that previously worked with us through the Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI) consulting services (see [11], [12]). We aimed for a diverse sample of participants from our population of 39 consulting engagements. When looking across previous engagements, we focused on 3 characteristics to achieve diversity: (1) the disciplinary context of the gateway; (2) the time of the consulting engagement; and (3) the maturity of the gateway at the time of consulting. We attempted to avoid selecting projects that were too similar across one or more of these dimensions. After mapping the projects across these dimensions, we identified a set of 25 projects that represented the best diversity from our population. All 25 teams were invited to participate in our study via email. Of the 25, 18 agreed to participate.

Once participants agreed to participate, they signed a study consent form and then filled out a brief survey. The survey collected basic information including the participant's role in the gateway, how long the participant has been involved in the gateway, the maturity of the gateway, the funding situation for the gateway, and the current software development support they have. Answers to these questions provided helpful information for the interviews.

Interviews were carried out from July 2021 through October 2021. Interviews were semi-structured and conducted remotely via videoconferencing. All interviews were recorded and then transcribed using an automated service called Otter.ai [14]. The interview protocol was developed based on our experiences with the consulting engagements, our understanding of the current literature, and our knowledge of cyberinfrastructure projects in general. The protocol consisted of three main topics: perceptions of UX, implementation barriers, and team factors. We started off by asking participants to provide a high-level overview of their gateway, and then what led them to seek out usability consulting services.

For the first topic, we asked questions about their knowledge and perception of the value of UX: what their knowledge of UX was prior to working with us, whether their knowledge changed as a result, whether their perceptions of the *value*, *role*, and *importance* of UX changed, and whether their future grant proposal strategies would change to account more for UX. For the second topic, we were primarily interested in how UX recommendations were implemented—in other words, what the “handoff” from us to the team looked like, and what challenges might exist in implementing UX recommendations. We asked participants to describe what happened during the consulting engagement, after they received final reports from the UX team, what their team discussions were like, how they made decisions about what to prioritize, and what barriers there were to taking action on recommendations that were given.

A. Participants

Eighteen participants were interviewed as part of this study. Table I provides details about each participant, including

the disciplinary alignment of their gateway, their team size, gateway age, and when the consulting engagement took place. We achieved a relatively diverse sample, with gateways coming from several disciplines; a mix of smaller and larger team sizes; and a range of gateway maturity, including new gateways still in pre-release stage to gateways that have been in operation for more than 10 years; and engagements across the range of time in which we operated.

B. Analysis

Interviews lasted 55 minutes on average, with a range of 27 to 88 minutes. Collectively, the interviews were approximately 16 hours. All interviews were conducted by the lead author, and student researchers participated as note-takers across a range of the interviews. After transcription, transcripts were examined and errors and fixed manually by the research team. Once transcripts were corrected, they were loaded into a qualitative data analysis platform called Dovetail [15]. Transcripts were analyzed using hybrid thematic analysis [13], incorporating both bottom-up and top-down approaches.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Understanding of UX

The majority of participants indicated a lack of familiarity with the concepts and practices of UX and usability. One participant described it as: “I think the concepts of UX are unfamiliar to a lot of people who are not kind of in the field”, then, when continuing the discussion, used the two concepts as interchangeable: “I had learned a lot and that was my first exposure to this whole usability field.” Another participant stated: “I had no idea before what it's [UX] for, and we learned a lot in terms of how people gather information on the interface is really critical to their learning process.” Another participant described how PIs often do not have familiarity because they are focused on the scientific aspects of the work: “Most of the PIs on this have little or no experience doing this kind of user interface, or user focus work. They're really people who do, you know, do science.”

Others described some awareness about what UX entails, although still at a superficial level. For example, a participant described their team's understanding of UX as: “we did not have an idea that it was super important beyond, you know, make it colorblind friendly, or whatever. But we weren't really aware of any design principles we should be following other than a vague idea of what we've seen on other websites, but not really knowing explicitly what those elements were.” Others indicated a little more understanding, going from ‘look and feel’ to the importance of discoverability: “I think that we primarily focused on the look and feel. And then, you know, we're always hearing that it's difficult to find things on the website. And so it kind of like, we need to make it easier for people to find things. But we didn't really know how to do that, or what that really meant.” Similarly, a different participant described it as “knowing our website didn't look great, but not really understanding what or how we could improve it.”

TABLE I

GATEWAY CHARACTERISTICS FOR THE 18 PARTICIPANTS IN OUR STUDY: DISCIPLINARY ALIGNMENT OR CONTEXT OF GATEWAY; SIZE OF GATEWAY TEAM (PEOPLE); GATEWAY AGE (YEARS OF OPERATION); START DATE OF CONSULTING ENGAGEMENT. EACH ROW REPRESENTS ONE PARTICIPANT. PARTICIPANT IDS REMOVED TO MAINTAIN ANONYMITY

Disciplinary Alignment	Team Size	Gateway Age	Consulting Date
Oceanography/Geology	6-9	1-2	2021
Environmental/Ecological	6-9	6+	2021
Psychology/Genetics	3-5	<1	2020
Hydrology	10+	6+	2020
Environmental Science/Resource Management	3-5	6+	2020
Interdisciplinary Health	4-5	<1	2020
Microbiology/Data Science	10+	1-2	2020
Agriculture/Data Science	6-9	3-5	2020
Interdisciplinary Oceanography	1-2	3-5	2018
Hydrology/Geophysics	1-2	3-5	2019
Geoscience	3-5	3-5	2019
Ecology/Sociology	3-5	6+	2020
Ecology	1-2	1-2	2019
Ecology	3-5	6+	2020
Atmosphere Science	3-5	<1	2020
Wildlife Ecology	10+	6+	2020
Plant Biology	3-5	<1	2020
Resource Management	3-5	<1	2020

B. Value of UX

When asked about the value they put on UX and usability after working with our consulting team, one participant stated “absolutely, I can’t overstate how important we feel usability is.” Being shown the strategies and outcomes of UX work, this participant came to understand the value that usability and a design-oriented approach holds. Usability is not just a factor to consider, but an important concept that is essential to a platform’s success. This user also mentioned focusing on usability-centered design going forward with their project, and their projects should be usability-focused from the start: “it [usability] has got to be centered in there from day one.”

This leads to the important idea of where usability and UX fit into the planning and development process for science gateways, as exemplified by another participant: “At that point [during the design and development process], we know that we need to create some sort of version of this interface. And then we have to go and do some proper usability testing to understand, you know, does the manner in which information is being shown really, is that the way we want to go? Or do we make some big changes in how we’re thinking about how our end users will interact with the interactive platform?” This highlights a fundamental aspect of UX that is often misunderstood or oversimplified within gateway development. While there is awareness of the importance of the user experience, this awareness frequently manifests at a later stage in the design process, after a gateway is already launched and problems are noticed. This approach exemplifies a reactive rather than proactive stance on UX, where it is considered a subsequent checkpoint rather than an integral, ongoing component of the design process. Another participant echoes this sentiment, stating how gateways folks “may have thought that this [UX] was kind of this add on.” Such a viewpoint can treat UX as an optional enhancement—or even an afterthought—rather than a critical component of the development process.

V. DISCUSSION

A. UX Knowledge

Many participants commented on how little they knew about usability and UX before working with us. For participants that did have familiarity with these concepts, it was often limited to a focus on the ‘look and feel’ of product and the evaluation of it via usability testing. In other words, it was limited to usability, and even more limited on its evaluation late in the development process (rather than a proactive, design-oriented approach to user experience). Expanding conceptions of what it means to do user-centered kind of work can allow gateways creators to think more proactively about the value their platforms can bring to their community—e.g., thinking early on about who the target users are; what their goals and needs are; what opportunities and challenge exist in meeting those needs; what kinds of features might be useful, and how they should be organized coherently. These concerns all go beyond narrow conceptions of usability, and especially notions of considering usability only after a product is developed. We do not suggest that gateways PIs and developers need to become experts on UX; simply recognizing the broad range of concepts and methods—and the proactive, design-first approach—can help them find the right people to include in the planning and development of gateways projects.

B. Priorities

Several participants described having priorities other than those related to the user experience. For example, one of the participants described how their gateway has prioritized functionality (‘does it work’) over the user experience: “I would say we functioned a lot more on just does it work versus would the user be able to understand how to use it without detailed help guidance.” This kind of approach exemplifies the so-called ‘system-centered design’ (vs. user-centered design) approach, where technical features and capabilities are

considered first, then the needs and preferences of users and other stakeholders are considered later. This approach is often accompanied by an expectation that users should read a manual. There are historical examples of systems with impressive technical capabilities that failed due to attending to user experience concerns too late or as a second priority (e.g., see Doug Engelbart’s “Mother of all demos” that was eventually abandoned by ARPA).

C. Proactive vs Reactive Approach to UX

The insights gathered from our interviews indicate that while there is growing awareness of the importance of usability and user experience (UX) in science gateway development, there remains a need for a broader and more comprehensive understanding of UX. Expanding beyond usability testing, which is often conducted post-development, involves planning ahead and considering various use cases to ensure the user experience is an ongoing concern throughout the development cycle. Effective UX design requires incorporating problem framing and user research early in the process to gain a deep understanding of the target audience’s needs and behaviors. After consulting with us, one participant recognized the importance of considering UX early, stating that it “seems like the most efficient thing, because I don’t want to have to go back and fix problems. I would rather not build in the problems in the first place.” This proactive, user-centered and design-oriented approach contributes to the sustainability of science gateways by ensuring that platforms are adaptable and resilient to changing requirements and technological advancements.

VI. CONCLUSION

Our study aims to shed light on the current understanding and perceptions of user experience (UX) among science gateway personnel. Despite the growing recognition of usability concerns within the community, there exists a significant gap in knowledge and awareness regarding the broader concepts and practices of UX. Many participants expressed limited familiarity with UX, highlighting the need for education and awareness-building initiatives within the science gateways community to leverage the full potential of UX in improving gateway design and functionality.

Our findings emphasize the critical importance of integrating UX considerations early in the development process rather than treating them as an afterthought. A proactive approach to UX, encompassing thorough user research, problem framing, and continuous feedback loops, is essential for creating effective and user-friendly science gateways. By prioritizing UX from the outset, teams can ensure that user needs are addressed comprehensively, leading to more sustainable projects.

We encourage science gateway personnel to recognize the value of UX practices and incorporate them into project planning stages. While they may not need to become UX experts themselves, understanding the fundamentals of UX enables them to make informed decisions about hiring the right professionals and allocating resources effectively. By fostering a culture of UX awareness and integration, science gateways

can enhance their overall quality and impact, ultimately benefiting both users and stakeholders alike.

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